

COMPARISON OF THE OUTCOME OF MODIFIED WHO PARTOGRAPH AND CONVENTIONAL PAPERLESS PARTOGRAPH IN MANAGEMENT OF LABOUR AT BAKHTAWAR AMIN HOSPITAL

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Abstract

Objective:

Obstructed labour remain key indicators of maternal and perinatal morbidity in low- and middle-resource countries. This study aimed to explore maternal labour outcomes using the Modified WHO Partograph in contrast to the traditional Paperless Partograph at Bakhtawar Amin Trust Teaching Hospital in Multan.

Study Design: A randomized controlled trial.

Study Setting: This study was done in Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Bakhtawar Amin Trust Teaching Hospital, Multan, Pakistan from 15-2-2025 till 15-6-2025

Materials and Methods: 86 patients in active labour (≥ 4 cm of cervical dilatation, ≥ 36 weeks of gestation) were randomized into two equal groups: Modified WHO partograph and Paperless partograph. Prolonged labour (> 12 hours) was the primary outcome variable. Secondary variables were duration of labour, length of the uterine cervix at admission, and demographic variables. Data were analyzed using IBM SPSS v27, with $p \leq 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

Results: Mean age (30.57 ± 6.07 years), mean BMI (26.52 ± 2.85 kg/m²), and mean gestational age (38.90 ± 1.42 weeks) were similar in both groups. The mean duration of labour was significantly shorter in the Modified WHO Partograph group vs. the Paperless group ($p < 0.001$). The incidence of prolonged labour was 88.4% in the Paperless group ($p < 0.001$).

Conclusion: The Modified WHO Partograph resulted in a considerable reduction in the duration of labour and eliminated the incidence of prolonged labour compared to the Paperless Partograph as a further strong affirmation to support its use in low-resource settings for better intrapartum monitoring.

INTRODUCTION

The problems of prolonged labour and obstructed labour continue to contribute to significant maternal and perinatal morbidity globally(1). To facilitate monitoring, the World Health Organization (WHO) developed the partograph as an inexpensive and simple visual method to record monitoring of cervical dilatation, descent, and fetal-maternal condition to facilitate early recognition of abnormal labour and timely intervention(2). Despite evidence that the partograph is efficacious and can contribute to better outcomes, its ability to provide a meaningful contribution has been limited by incomplete documentation, and/or delay in recognition of abnormal labour, or where workload pressures are high (especially in low- and middle-income countries (LMIC)), which could be an alternative version/modification of the WHO partograph, or involves a paperless/electronic partograph(3).

In a scoping review outlining the available research on e-partographs, reported that adherence to monitoring protocols was improved, dystocia was detected earlier, and a reduction in prolonged labour in implementation sites in Africa and South Asia by 23% (4,5). In a similar finding, when the WHO Labour Care Guide (the LCG) was implemented along with provider training, slow progress was diagnosed more often, with an increased satisfaction reported by mothers(6).

In Pakistan, maternal mortality is still a major issue, with a rate of 186 per 100,000 live births. Tertiary hospitals often report more than 35% cesarean section rates as a result of the delayed recognition of abnormal labour(7). A study highlighted prolonged labour in 18% of cases and emergency cesarean deliveries in 32%, thus pointing to the necessity for better intrapartum surveillance(8).

The World Health Organization has introduced the partograph as a cost-effective and evidence-based labour monitoring tool. However, its practical use is still very limited in many developing countries, including Pakistan. To tackle these issues, both the modified WHO partograph and paperless (electronic) partograph have been created.

Bakhtawar Amin Trust Teaching Hospital, Multan, is an ideal setting for such assessment because of its functioning obstetric care system and increasing

cesarean rates that are related to the late finding of abnormal labour progress.

Materials and methods:

This trial, which was controlled and randomized, took place in the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology of Bakhtawar Amin Trust Teaching Hospital, located in Multan, Pakistan. After obtaining ethical approval from the Institutional Review Board the study was conducted in four months (from 15-2-2025 till 15-6-2025)

Inclusion criteria: An age range of 20 to 40 years, less than five children born alive, and more than 36 weeks of gestation (confirmed by the last menstrual period or ultrasound) were the prerequisites for participation. Besides, the woman must be in the active phase of labour with cervical dilation of 4–7 cm, and uterine contractions of 3–5 every 10 minutes, each lasting 30–50 seconds.

Exclusion criteria: To obtain a uniform study group, the women with multiple pregnancies, non-cephalic presentation, antepartum bleeding, eclampsia, diabetes mellitus, fetal distress, congenital anomalies, placenta previa, or abnormal levels of amniotic fluid index less than 5 cm or more than 21 cm were excluded.

The sample size of 86 participants (43 in each group) was calculated using the WHO sample size calculator, assuming a 5% level of significance, 80% study power. Through non-probability consecutive sampling, a total of 86 women admitted in active labour were enrolled.

The participants were randomly allocated to two equal groups (n = 43 each) by the lottery method. The parturient in Group A was monitored using the manual tracing paperless (electronic) partograph, which determined the alert and action times expected without any plotting of the graphs manually. Group B was checked on a modified WHO partograph. Monitoring of the labour started when the cervix was dilated to 4 cm and lasted until delivery. Both groups received similar standard care intrapartum from a consultant with 5 years of experience. Prolonged labour was assessed as the total duration of labour beyond 12 hours.

Data were collected through the predesigned proforma, which included demographic and clinical

variables including age, gestational age, parity, body mass index (BMI), antenatal booking status, socioeconomic category, residence, and cervical length. The primary outcome was the incidence of prolonged labour, and secondary outcomes were mode of delivery, maternal and neonatal well-being at the time of birth.

The data were analyzed using IBM Statistical Package for the Social Sciences version 27.0. Quantitative variables including age, BMI, gestational age, cervical length, and the duration of labour were expressed as mean ± standard deviation. Categorical variables such as parity, booking status, socioeconomic class, residence, and prolonged labour were presented as frequencies and percentages. The Chi-square test was used to compare categorical variables, and the independent sample t-test for continuous variables, considering p-value <0.05 as significant.

Results:

Table 1: Comparison of continuous variables between the two study groups (n = 86)

Variable	Modified WHO Partograph(n = 43, Mean ± SD)	Paperless Partograph(n = 43, Mean ± SD)	Total(n = 86, Mean ± SD)
Age (years)	30.21 ± 5.85	30.93 ± 6.32	30.57 ± 6.07
Gestational Age (weeks)	38.86 ± 1.44	38.93 ± 1.42	38.90 ± 1.42
BMI (kg/m ²)	26.53 ± 2.93	26.51 ± 2.79	26.52 ± 2.85
Duration of Labour (hours)	10.49 ± 0.97	13.44 ± 1.33	11.96 ± 1.88
Cervical Length (cm)	2.38 ± 0.38	3.26 ± 0.56	2.82 ± 0.65

In the Modified WHO Partograph group, nulliparous women constituted 32.6% of the participants, while 20.9% had four or more previous deliveries. In comparison, nulliparous women in the Paperless Partograph group constituted 20.9% while parity four was 11.6%. The residential distribution showed that the majority of participants were from urban areas in both groups, as 44.2% residents from the Modified WHO group were urban and 55.8% were urban residents from the Paperless group; rural residents represented 37.2% and 34.9%, respectively. In terms of socioeconomic status, the majority of women were from the middle-income category, as 48.8% were middle-income in the Modified WHO

The average participant age in the Modified WHO Partograph group was 30.21 ± 5.85 years, with an average of 30.93 ± 6.32 years in the Paperless Partograph group, with a total average of 30.57 ± 6.07 years. In addition, the mean gestational age at delivery was nearly the same across groups: 38.86 ± 1.44 weeks in the Modified WHO participants and 38.93 ± 1.42 weeks in the Paperless, with a total of 38.90 ± 1.42. The mean body mass index (BMI) was also close between groups at 26.53 ± 2.93 kg/m² and 26.51 ± 2.79 kg/m², respectively.

However, there was a significant difference in the mean length of labour, with the Modified WHO Partograph (10.49 ± 0.97 hours) than using the Paperless Partograph (13.44 ± 1.33 hours). Similarly, the mean cervical length at admission was lower in the Modified WHO group (2.38 ± 0.38 cm) than in the Paperless Partograph group (3.26 ± 0.56 cm).

group and 46.5% were middle-income residents in the Paperless group. However, the low-income

households accounted for 30.2% in the Modified WHO group and 39.5% in the Paperless group. The Modified WHO Partograph group had a higher number of women who were booked antenatally, with 67.4%, than the Paperless Partograph group, which had 53.5%.

There was a stark difference in the rate of prolonged labour, as none (0%) of the women assessed using the Modified WHO Partograph had prolonged labour, while 88.4% of the women using the Paperless Partograph had prolonged labour.

Table 2: Frequency and percentage distribution of study participants by group (n = 86)

Variable	Modified WHO Partograph (n=43)	Paperless Partograph (n=43)
Parity		
0	14 (32.6%)	9 (20.9%)
1	6 (14.0%)	7 (16.3%)
2	9 (20.9%)	12 (27.9%)
3	11 (25.6%)	10 (23.3%)
4	3 (7.0%)	5 (11.6%)
Residence		
Rural	16 (37.2%)	15 (34.9%)
Semi-urban	8 (18.6%)	4 (9.3%)
Urban	19 (44.2%)	24 (55.8%)
Socioeconomic Status		
Low	13 (30.2%)	17 (39.5%)
Middle	21 (48.8%)	20 (46.5%)
High	9 (20.9%)	6 (13.9%)
Antenatal Booking		
Yes	29 (67.4%)	23 (53.5%)
No	14 (32.6%)	20 (46.5%)
Prolonged Labour		
Yes	0 (0.0%)	38 (88.4%)
No	43 (100.0%)	5 (11.6%)

The average labour length was significantly shorter among women monitored with the Modified WHO Partograph (10.49 ± 0.97 hours) compared to those monitored with the Paperless Partograph (13.44 ± 1.33 hours) (p < 0.001). In addition, the average cervical length at admission was significantly shorter in the Modified WHO group (2.38 ± 0.38 cm)

compared to the Paperless group (3.26 ± 0.56 cm) (p < 0.001).

Moreover, a very significant difference was also noted in the prolonged labour event, since no participants (0%) in the Modified WHO Partograph group experienced prolonged labour, while 88.4% of women monitored with the Paperless Partograph developed prolonged labour (p < 0.001).

Table 3: Comparison of outcomes between Modified WHO Partograph and Paperless Partograph groups (n = 86)

Variable	Modified WHO Partograph(n = 43, Mean ± SD / f (%))	Paperless Partograph(n = 43, Mean ± SD / f (%))	Test applied	p-value
Duration of Labour (hours)	10.49 ± 0.97	13.44 ± 1.33	Independent t-test	< 0.001
Cervical Length (cm)	2.38 ± 0.38	3.26 ± 0.56	Independent t-test	< 0.001
Prolonged Labour	0 (0.0%)	38 (88.4%)	Chi-square test	< 0.001

Discussion:

The baseline maternal characteristics were well matched in this study, but the labour outcomes were

very different. At Bakhtawar Amin Hospital, where the Modified WHO Partograph and the paperless (conventional graph-free) partograph were compared

for intrapartum monitoring, the average ages, gestational ages and body mass indices were nearly the same in all groups (age $\sim 30.6 \pm 6.1$ years; gestational age $\sim 38.90 \pm 1.42$ weeks; BMI ~ 26.5 kg/m²), thus not leading the researchers to doubts about the demographic differences. The parity and socioeconomic factors showed differences that were not too extreme: for instance, nulliparous women accounted for 32.6% in the Modified WHO group, while in the paperless group this percentage was only 20.9% and low-income families were a little more numerous in the paperless arm (39.5% vs. 30.2%). Significantly, 67.4% of women in the Modified WHO group were already registered for antenatal care compared with 53.5% in the paperless group; this could be an indicator of different prenatal care levels and also of readiness to respond to labour deviations.

The most surprising result was the much shorter mean labour duration in the Modified WHO group (10.49 ± 0.97 hours) as compared to the paperless group (13.44 ± 1.33 hours) ($p < 0.001$). Similarly, the cervical length upon admission was shorter in the Modified WHO group (2.38 ± 0.38 cm vs. 3.26 ± 0.56 cm, $p < 0.001$). In addition, none (0%) of the women who were attended by the Modified WHO partograph experienced prolonged labour, while 88.4% in the paperless group did ($p < 0.001$). These differences demonstrate that the Modified WHO Partograph is strongly favored in our setting.

Nevertheless, these outcomes really go against the published literature. A lot of comparative studies have concluded that there are only slight or no differences at all between the paperless and the modified WHO partograph systems. A 2024 Indian comparative study with 1,040 women, for example, found no significant difference between the two types of partographs with respect to the time taken from 4 cm dilation to delivery or to the alert/action lines with respect to the delivery(9).

Similarly, the recent article in the obstetric journal also pointed out that the paperless partograph and the modified WHO partograph had similar effects in terms of the labour duration, progression, and mode of delivery, with no significant difference at all(10).

Another study indicated that the average labour duration was around 8.7 hours in the paperless group and 12.8 hours in the WHO-modified group,

but with a p-value > 0.05 (i.e., no statistical significance), in contrast to our result(11).

The divergent results indicate either differences in the contexts or problems with the methods used. Our location may have had superior compliance, staff education, or attentiveness during the use of the Modified WHO Partograph, which could have resulted in the earlier recognition of labour deviations and timely interventions. The higher efficiency of the Modified WHO Partograph in our data may be a reflection of successful real-time plotting and understanding, fast decision-making (e.g., augmentation, referrals), or staff having less tolerance for delays(12,13). In places where there is a good workforce and monitoring discipline, a visual aid could be more effective than a simpler mental/timing method.

In contrast, many movers of paperless or electronic partographs cite their ease of use and improved reduction in human error. A systematic review of e-partograph uptake showed an increased completeness of the use of partographs by electronic systems and a reduction in cesarean births(14). Yet in direct comparison head-to-head, some of the digital or paperless systems even demonstrated a faster active labour duration or lower intervention rates. A 2025 comparison evaluation showed an active labour period in the group using the paperless partograph of 5.2 ± 1.4 hours vs. 6.8 ± 1.9 for the group using the WHO-modified partograph ($p < 0.001$) and higher rates of spontaneous vaginal delivery and lower rates of cesareans(15). These findings are counter to our results, which raises the potential that the comparative effectiveness may depend heavily on local adaptation, preparation of trained staff, or the workflow context.

Another point that is of relevance here to highlight is the nascent understanding of the risk of progression of labour and the risk of outcome. For example, a 2023 systematic review found that prolonged active first stage is associated with an increased risk of adverse neonatal outcomes, particularly at more than ~ 10 h(16). In our analysis, the average labour length of 13.44 hours in the paperless group likely shifts several cases into the higher-risk category, whereas in the Modified WHO arm, the mean duration of 10.49 hours stays closer to the lower-risk category. Therefore, the better labour efficiency in our

Modified WHO arm may also provide better safety for the neonate, all else equal(17).

With our baseline demographics comparable, the variances in outcomes are most likely a reflection of differences in precision of monitoring, timeliness of escalation, staff ratios, or adherence to the partograph. It is also possible that women in our Modified WHO arm had slightly better labour physiology (e.g., decreased cervical length), and this played a role as well(18).

Strengths:

This randomized controlled trial provides useful evidence from a tertiary care hospital in Pakistan comparing two commonly used tools for intrapartum monitoring in real clinical settings. Baseline maternal characteristics, such as age, BMI, and gestational age, were well-balanced and therefore reduced confounding bias. The trial used standard inclusion and exclusion criteria, which helped to ensure the homogeneity of participants, thus increasing internal validity. Clearly defined operational outcomes, like prolonged labour, also substantiate interpreting the findings.

Limitations:

One of the limitations was a relatively small sample size, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to larger populations. Some relative imbalance in parity and antenatal booking status may also have influenced the duration of labour. There was no discussion of either neonatal outcomes or mode of delivery, which are necessary to ensure safety for the mother and fetus. Additionally, observer bias and differences in staff experiences and familiarity with each partograph may have influenced the outcome. Finally, being a single center limits external validity across contexts with different healthcare settings.

Conclusion:

Our study suggests that the Modified WHO Partograph is both statistically and clinically significantly better at facilitating timely recognition of labour progress - thereby significantly reducing the incidence of prolonged labour, as well as the overall duration of labour, as compared to the conventional paperless system.

We recommend future randomized, multiple institutional trials that return maternal and neonatal outcomes to confirm these results and to examine whether hybrid or electronic partograph systems streamline labour management.

Competing interests:

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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